

Covid-19: A Data Scientist Perspective

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Abstract

The outbreak of Coronavirus (Covid-19) continues to spread globally across international boundaries. This pandemic has significantly affected mankind across the globe. Owing to a short term experience with this virus, the whole world is struggling hard to analyze its behaviour. Top leading pharmaceutical companies have been trying really hard to formulate the vaccine for this virus. Apart from medical professionals, researchers from other fields are also fascinated toward this. For instance, data scientists are putting rigorous efforts to analyze the rising trend of the virus, its impact on the international economy, and much more. An efficient analysis will enable us to have accurate predictions so that nations can be well prepared in order to handle this virus.

In this session, we are going to discuss the Covid-19 from the perspective of a data scientist. The focus of this discussion is how data scientists may use the historical data (since emergence of Covid-19) to devise some forecasting models so that health sectors in the nation remain well prepared. It will also discuss the impact of Covid-19 on the national and global economy.